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1. Executive Summary

The GUTTA kick-off (KO) consisted of two linked but separate events: a public opening conference and an internal meeting. Both took place in Lecce, Italy, from March 6 to 8, 2019.

Scope of the public conference was to provide a broader framework into which forthcoming GUTTA project activities will be placed and to establish links with other European Projects.

Scope of the internal meeting was to present Project Partners' expertise, to critically review WP activities, and to provide information for project day-to-day management, financial reporting and internal communication, as well as taking decisions and actions for the initial implementation activities of GUTTA.

Participation of several high school students (to the public conference) and an EMSA representative (to both public conference and internal meeting) enriched the outreach and the productivity of the KO.

In the Annex to this report, the letter sent by EMSA Executive Director to the GUTTA Coordinator stating the availability to be part of the GUTTA Advisory Board is attached.

For the shortcuts employed in this report, we refer to the official GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1pEbyf1Rb7gAo8nyGAYfT_PyVqKrxFXkx

2. Opening Conference (March 6, 8:30-13:30)

The event is here documented by means of its agenda, list of participants, main outcomes, and online published contents.

2.1 Agenda

Session A	Towards a sustainable Adriatic transportation
	Hotel Risorgimento, via A. Imperatore 19 Lecce
	March 6, 8:30-13:30
	<i>Scope of the public conference is to provide a broader framework into which GUTTA project activities will be placed and to establish links with other European Projects</i>

8:30 - 9:00	Registration
9:00	Introduction and chair <i>Paola Agostini (CMCC, Lecce – IT)</i>
9:05	Institutional greetings <i>Stefano Minerva (President of the Province of Lecce - IT)</i>
9:10	Apulia, Dalmatia, and the Adriatic Sea as a shared History <i>Egidio Ivetic (University of Padua - IT)</i>
9:40	Impacts of anthropogenic climate change in Europe <i>Enrico Scoccimarro (CMCC, Bologna - IT)</i>
10:10	The Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service <i>Giovanni Coppini (CMCC, Lecce - IT)</i>
10:40	Coffee Break
11:10	Underwater noise and marine mammals in the Adriatic Sea: the SOUNDSCAPE project <i>Nikolina Rako (Blue World Institute, Veli Lošinj – HR)</i>
11:40	The European Maritime Safety Agency and the MRV Regulation (EU 757/2015) <i>Miguel Madeira (EMSA, Lisbon - PT)</i>
12:10	Sea Traffic Management as a tool for emissions savings <i>Ulf Svedberg (Swedish Maritime Administration - SE)</i>
12:40	VISIR and sustainable maritime transportation <i>Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC, Lecce - IT)</i>
13:10	Concluding remarks <i>Giovanni Indiveri (University of Salento- IT)</i>

2.2 Participants

The conference had 43 registered participants. Among them, 11 students from a high school in the Province of Lecce, Istituto Tecnico Trasporti e Logistica “Amerigo Vespucci” in Galiipoli. They are part of the “under-40 EU citizens” communication target group of the GUTTA Strategy. The full list of participants is given in Figure 1.

Table 1. LP archives the original signed registration sheets.

Portraits of the speakers of the conference taken by Loredana Cocola (CMCC) are displayed in Figure 1.

Table 1 List of participants to the opening conference of the GUTTA project.

No.	Name	Surname	Organization
1	Enrico	Scoccimarro	CMCC
2	Ulf	Svedberg	SMA
3	Mladena	Maračić	HR Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure
4	Davor	Deželjin	HR Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure
5	Benedicte	Madon	UBO
6	Martin	Zrilic	UniZD
7	Zoran	Pavin	UniZD
8	Josip	Orović	UniZD
9	Miguel	Madeira	EMSA
10	Gianandrea	Mannarini	CMCC
11	Nikolina	Rako Gospić	Blue World Institute
12	Salvatore	Causio	CMCC
13	Egidio	Ivetic	University of Padua
14	Stelvio	Carmagnola	Istituto Tecnico "Amerigo Vespucci", Gallipoli
15	Simone	Bove	Istituto Tecnico "Amerigo Vespucci", Gallipoli
16	Maria	Mihalic	CSA Mare Nostrum
17	Sandro	Vidas	CSA Mare Nostrum
18	Giovanni	Indiveri	UniSalento
19	Alessandro	De Benedetto	Istituto Tecnico "Amerigo Vespucci", Gallipoli
20	Lorenzo	Piccione	Istituto Tecnico "Amerigo Vespucci", Gallipoli
21	Eric	Jansen	CMCC
22	Letizia	Lusito	UniSalento
23	Giorgio	Galati	Istituto Tecnico "Amerigo Vespucci", Gallipoli
24	Giovanni	Coppini	CMCC
25	Roberto	Bonarelli	CMCC
26	Francesco	Palermo	CMCC
27	Farshid	Daryabor	CMCC
28	Ivano	Barletta	CMCC
29	Lorenzo	Carelli	CMCC
30	Alessandro	D'Anca	CMCC
31	Riccardo	Carelli	-
32	Fabio	Montagna	CMCC
33	Samuele	De Bartolo	UniSalento
34	Fulvio	Nuzzo	Istituto Tecnico "Amerigo Vespucci", Gallipoli

35	Roberta	Besanti	Istituto Tecnico “Amerigo Vespucci”, Gallipoli
36	Ivan	Federico	CMCC
37	Alessia	Cuppone	Istituto Tecnico “Amerigo Vespucci”, Gallipoli
38	Silvia	Finiguerra	Istituto Tecnico “Amerigo Vespucci”, Gallipoli
39	Andrea	Leone	Istituto Tecnico “Amerigo Vespucci”, Gallipoli
40	Mario	Sansò	Istituto Tecnico “Amerigo Vespucci”, Gallipoli
41	Paola	Agostini	CMCC
42	Bruno	Pellegrino	UniSalento
43	Sergio	Cretì	CMCC

Figure 1 Speakers of the GUTTA opening conference: from top left: Paola Agostini, Egidio Ivetic, Enrico Scoccimarro, Giovanni Coppini, Nikolina Rako, Ulf Svedberg, Miguel Madeira, Gianandrea Mannarini, Giovanni Indiveri

2.3 Main outcomes

The conference ran on schedule and each Speaker received at least one question. There was plenty of opportunity for informal exchange and networking during the 30-min coffee break. Participants

expressed general satisfaction with respect to conference contents and organization, which allowed to get informed about different aspects of sustainable maritime transportation in the Adriatic Sea.

The key messages by each speaker are summarized in the following:

Agostini

She introduced the three GUTTA project specific objectives and its communication target groups.

Minerva

He shared a personal reflection upon the Adriatic Sea history, which is rich in conflicts and opportunities, including the modern dimension of environmental sustainability of this sea.

Ivetic

He depicted the Adriatic space as a system of economic inter-dependencies, no matter the specific political situation realized across the centuries. In particular, he highlighted a few common heritages, including the Dalmatian stone, and some religious links (Loreto sanctuary and Saint Nicholas) which are important to peoples on both shores of the Adriatic.

Scoccimarro

He introduced anthropogenic climate change and presented results of the CMCC-CM2 model for years 2060-2100 (this time-window is needed for filtering internal variability of the climate system). In particular, he showed increases in the perceived temperature HUMIDEX index in Europe. These results are backed by comparison with the COSMO-CLM regional model.

Coppini

He presented the historical evolution of the European capacity in ocean observing and predicting, starting from the Baveno Manifesto (2008) to the Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES) to the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS). At the end of this long chain, applications have arisen during the last decade, including oil spill forecasting, optimal ship routing, and ocean literacy initiatives (Copernicus Academy).

Rako

She provided an introduction to underwater sound, its specificity, origin and use by marine animals. In particular, she stated that noise from human activities has increased by 3dB each decade. The impact on

natural ecosystem is very diverse depending among others on frequency, duration, distance to source, specific animal hearing capability. This motivates the development of a network of passive acoustic monitoring network, observation of local fauna, and restoring initiatives in the Northern Adriatic supported by Italy-Croatia SOUNDSCAPE project (Programme Specific Objective 3.2).

Madeira

He presented EMSA institutional activities and the consultation process which led to the definition of the EU MRV Regulation. In particular, the role of the European Sustainable Shipping Forum (ESSF) was stressed. In fact, EMSA considers links with both academia and industry necessary for accomplishing its tasks. Then, the main features of the Thetis-MRV system were presented. The contents of the recent proposal for alignment of EU MRV with IMO DCS was also summarized.

Svedberg

He made a general introduction on shipping efficiency, starting from the example of exploitation of horse power. Then he presented the STM (Sea Traffic Management) framework for information exchange, with the RTZ standard format¹ which is now accepted on all new ECDIS (Electronic Chart Display and Information Systems). Some recent applications of STM for transmission of SAR (Search-And-Rescue) patterns and navigation in PSSA (Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas) were also shown.

Mannarini

He made a review of European GHG reduction targets till 2050 and verification of their implementation by the EEA (European Environmental Agency). While EU is on-track for achieving its 2020 target, it will not be able to match the 2030 objective. For the transport sector, even a growth of the emissions is observed. He then presented recent advancements of the VISIR ship routing model meant to assess GHG savings by optimal use of ocean currents and waves.

Indiveri

He wrapped-up the conference by praising its inter-sectorial approach, allowing to get a “big picture” of maritime sustainability. He recommended to share online the presentations of the speakers and encouraged the spread of these contents as a best practice. In fact, even though this is just a drop (“gutta” in Latin means drop), it has the potential to have an impact on maritime transport.

¹ <http://cirm.org/rtz/index.html>

2.4 Online resources

Zenodo presentations: <https://zenodo.org/record/2592413>

Press release (cf. GUTTA deliverable D.2.1.1): <https://www.cmcc.it/article/clean-sustainable-safe-and-effective-the-future-of-maritime-transport-in-the-adriatic-sea-2>

3. Internal meeting

The event is here documented by means of its agenda, list of participants, main outcomes.

3.1 Agenda

Session B	Our legacy
	CMCC premises, via A. Imperatore 16 Lecce
	March 6, 15:00-17:30
	<i>Scope of each talk in this session will be to provide an overview of PP expertise, which will be employed for the implementation of the project.</i>
13:30	Light Lunch <i>reception at CMCC premises</i>
15:00	Energy efficient ship tracks in the Atlantic Ocean <i>Lorenzo Carelli (CMCC)</i>
15:30	Croatian shipowners in front of IMO and EU regulations for CO2 emission reduction <i>Sandro Vidas (CSA)</i>
16:00	Ro-Pax seakeeping and performance modeling <i>Josip Orovic (UniZd)</i>
16:30	Maritime certification and verification activities in Croatia <i>Mladena Maračić (MMPI)</i>
20:00	Social Dinner <i>Osteria della Divina Provvidenza, Via Francesco Rubichi 4, Lecce</i>

Session C	Our mission
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	CMCC premises, via A. Imperatore 16 Lecce
	March 7, 9:00-18:00
	<i>Scope of each WP block in this session will be a critical review of the WP activities and discussion of possible obstacles in the implementation. Each PP is required to prepare a list of potential issues prior to the kick-off meeting</i>
9:00	WP2: Communication activities Lead: AdSP MAM <i>Chair: Mauro Buonocore (CMCC)</i>
10:00	WP3: Strategic potential for a greener and more integrated CB maritime mobility Lead: UniZd <i>Chair: Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)</i>
11:00	Group Photo and coffee break
11:30	A deep dive into Thetis-MRV Miguel Madeira (EMSA)
11:45	WP4: Developing tools for upgrading environmental sustainability and connectivity of regional mobility Lead: CMCC <i>Chair: Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC)</i>
12:45	Light Lunch <i>reception at CMCC premises</i>
14:00	WP5: Demonstrating the change in environmental impact and territorial connectivity Lead: CSA <i>Chair: Paola Agostini (CMCC)</i>
15:00	Guided tour of the old town of Lecce - Discovering Roman, Christian, and Venetian footprints in the city <i>Tutor: Massimo Vergari;</i> <i>Interpreting into Croatian: Egidio Ivetic (UniPd)</i>

Session D	Next steps
	CMCC premises, via A. Imperatore 16 Lecce
	March 8, 8:30-11:30
	<i>Scope of this session is to provide the PP with practical information of project day-to-day management, financial reporting and internal communication</i>

8:30	WP1: Project management and coordination of activities Lead: CMCC <i>Chair: Paola Agostini (CMCC)</i>
10:30	Slack demo session <i>Fabio Montagna (CMCC)</i>

3.2 Participants

All PPs but AdSP participated to the kick-off meeting. AdSP could not participate because its internal administrative procedure could not be started before signature of the Subsidy Contract (which was signed only on March 12, 2019). EMSA delegate, Mr. Miguel Madeira, participated to the works of the partnership during two full days (Sessions B and C). The complete list of participants is given in Table 2. LP archives the original signed registration sheets.

Table 2 List of participants to the internal part of the GUTTA kick-off meeting

No.	Name	Surname	Organization
1	Maria	Mihalic	CSA Mare Nostrum
2	Sandro	Vidas	CSA Mare Nostrum
3	Mladena	Maračić	HR Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure
4	Davor	Deželjin	HR Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure
5	Martin	Zrilic	UniZD
6	Zoran	Pavin	UniZD
7	Josip	Orović	UniZD
8	Miguel	Madeira	EMSA
9	Gianandrea	Mannarini	CMCC
10	Lorenzo	Carelli	CMCC
11	Mauro	Buonocore	CMCC
12	Paola	Agostini	CMCC
13	Fabio	Montagna	CMCC

3.3 Main outcomes

Session B (March 6, 15:00-17:00)

In this session, the speakers presented Partner background expertise which is offered to the GUTTA partnership for the achievement of its objectives.

Carelli

He presented some recent results of the VISIR model relative to the AtlantOS project. He displayed track diversions due to waves and ocean currents, their seasonal and regional dependence, and the savings in voyage carbon intensity (quantified through the EEOI, Energy Efficient Operational Indicator, of IMO, International Maritime Organization) that they allow. The results are part of a comprehensive publication, currently under review, which can be openly accessed at:

Mannarini, G. and Carelli, L.: VISIR-I.b: waves and ocean currents for energy efficient navigation, Geosci. Model Dev. Discuss., <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-2018-292>, in review, 2019.

Vidas

He first briefly introduced the Croatian Shipowner Association, consisting of 10 among the leading Croatian companies of the maritime sector.

He then discussed the EU MRV Regulation from the viewpoint of the shipowners. In particular, he observed that data to be reported are much more compared to IMO DCS. While the EU MRV proposal of amendment is already finalized, IMO will take a decision on future strategy in 2021, upon analysis of fuel consumption data.

In relation to fuel type, he made the point that industry's investments on the propulsion system are tightly related to the specific fuel unit cost. This in turn depends on the fuel facilities available at ports, which can be very diverse worldwide. This makes the decision of global players difficult, as they operate on very different conditions in the various ports called by their vessels.

Finally, he reported about the Croatian investments for a LNG terminal in the island of Krk (Veglia in Italian) to be transported to Zadar via barge. He also mentioned possible implications for new CB routes calling at that area. In view of this, a Zadar-Venice route operated through a LNG vessel could be a quite appealing possibility.

Orović

He first reviewed existing CB ferry lines in the Adriatic and main parameters of some major vessels operating there. He then made a compact presentation of a vessel propulsion system and how its efficiency is related to many vessel internal and external parameters.

Finally, he addressed the point of assessing performance characteristics for the vessels of interest for the GUTTA project. In particular, he presented four options:

- 1) Use of trial/voyage data (very promising option but requires sensitive data which companies do not easily distribute or do not have)
- 2) Use of parametrizations from the literature (easiest option but least accurate)
- 3) Dedicated onboard measurement campaign (methodology still to be assessed and risk of limited statistical significance)
- 4) Simulator (good accuracy, but exact ferry type employed for CB routes probably not available)

Maračić

She reviewed the EU MRV Regulation in its three key phases of Monitoring/Reporting/Verification.

She then provided some insights on how MRV implementation is going on in Croatia:

- The first Monitoring phase, ended on 2018/12/31, ran smoothly. Two vessels in national trade are exempted from the obligation to monitor the information on a per-voyage basis (Art. 9, par. 2, MRV Regulation).
- The method chosen for determining CO2 emissions was “Bunker fuel tank monitoring on-board” (Method B in Annex I, Part B of EU Regulation 757/15)
- For the Reporting phase (ending 2019/04/30), most companies have already reported their emissions through the EMSA Thetis-MRV system.
- Croatian Register of Shipping is the accredited verifier for activities under the MRV Regulation by National Accreditation Body (Croatian Accreditation Agency) in accordance with the Regulation (EC) 765/2008.

Finally, she addressed the point of the new CB route to be facilitated by GUTTA. In this respect, MMPI can make available the traffic data from the CIMIS (which is the National counterpart of the SafeSeaNet system maintained by EMSA). In accordance with procedure and on the basis of existing interest of the ship-owner for the new CB RO-RO/passenger line, the “Agencija za obalni linijski pomorski promet” agency (<http://www.agencija-zolpp.hr>) will give a consent on a voyage plan for the new CB line.

Session C (March 7, 9:00-18:00)

This session addressed the implementation challenges for GUTTA project WP2-5.

Each WP was assigned one hour time for reviewing objectives, addressing potential obstacles, discussing solutions. The discussion was facilitated by Presentations for each WP, distributed already in the week before the KO meeting, and including:

- WP objectives
- WP activities
- WP deliverables
- Preliminary identification of WP open issues

Furthermore, the session comprised a technical deepening on Thetis MRV by the EMSA representative and a guided tour in the city of Lecce, for discovering some common CB cultural heritages.

WP2

Mauro Buonocore, starting from Italy-Croatia Programme Factsheet n.8, made the following points:

- the MA already envisioned a coherent communication strategy for the whole Italy-Croatia Interreg Programme projects;
- it is necessary that not just project deliverables, but also activities are disseminated (concept of “continuous communication”)
- WP2 is a collector of contributes from all other WPs
- In GUTTA we are committed to maintain a science-society dialogue
- all PPs should participate in the Communication activities

Sandro Vidas gave a preliminary availability of CSA for a SC meeting in Croatia in September 2019 with a public event under the umbrella of the EC-day 2019 (this year’s motto is “Europe is you”, cf. <https://www.ecday.eu>).

Miguel Madeira stated that EMSA contribution in GUTTA as member of the Advisory Board is in explaining-using-disseminating Thetis-MRV. Furthermore, he informed the group about an EMSA contact point for querying on the possibility of using EMSA footage for GUTTA videos.

The left open issues were the following ones:

- Communication contact points for each PP need to be defined
- If we do project videos (D.2.2.3), is it fine to just publish them online? Is it fine to develop an English language master version and then put subtitles in the two National languages? What is the total budget available for videos?

- An initial version of the Stakeholders database (D.2.1.1) was created by CMCC for the sake of inviting people to the opening conference. However, this deliverable is up to AdSP, which should probably update and maintain this database in the future.
- AdSP to be involved in the Communication management workflow as soon as they fix their administrative issues

Resolutions:

- a) Assigned some communication Contact points:
 - CMCC: Mauro Buonocore
 - UniZd: Martin Zrilić
 - EMSA: Ann MacPherson
 - MMPI: tbd
 - CSA: Maria Mihalić (tbc)

- b) Assigned responsible for some activities:
 - press-release: resp: PP Communication contact point
 - social media translations from English into Croatian: resp: CSA
 - video (and English translation) with footage from next SC meeting and footage filmed by UniZd during onboard measuring campaigns: resp: CSA

- c) Two videos or radio spots should be produced during the project:
 1. Containing aims of GUTTA and an invitation to join it as a stakeholder
 2. Disseminating GUTTA results, including interviews taken during SC and final events

WP3-4

WP3 and WP4 contain the core activity for achieving GUTTA specific objectives. WP3 work is preparatory and instrumental to WP4 where the actual project outputs are realized. Possibly, WP3 deliverables should be anticipated as much as possible, in order to leave time enough for WP4 and coping with unforeseen delays. For the same reason, next SC meeting is postponed from August (M08) to September 2019, in order to leave PPs time enough for finalizing many deliverables with deadline at M09. Also, some activities of WP4 related to D.4.1.1. (“analysis of the vessel performance database”, currently due at M20) should be anticipated in order to allow embedding into the new VISIR model code.

Sandro Vidas said that Jadrolinija is going to do its reporting towards Thetis-MRV on a per voyage basis. This data could possibly be of interest also for the development of the GUTTA eco-route tool. It is probably feasible to get historical performance/seakeeping data from a single vessel of Jadrolinija. Besides MMPI data (CiMIS), all other data sources should be exploited, in particular AIS data. How to get them?

Vidas also said that ferry normally sail straight between departure and arrival harbors. In case a track diversion is needed due to marine weather conditions, an approval of the modified voyage plan has to be previously granted by the relevant Authorities. Which Authorities should be contacted for deepening this?

Josip Orović asked for environmental fields which can be provided by CMCC. Gianandrea Mannarini listed following ones:

- sea state (wave height, direction, period)
- surface currents
- sea surface temperature
- water salinity
- wind (through the Italian MetOffice)

Miguel Madeira (EMSA) suggested to focus on interpretation/translation of the MRV Regulation in a simple language and on a customization of its legal requirements for a specific type of ship. EMSA is interested to get Thetis-MRV users feedbacks on the system that can be considered for future enhancements. This could be an appreciated outcome of GUTTA.

Resolutions:

For the vessel propulsion a seakeeping modeling, a layered approach should be adopted:

- V0 : from literature review, devise a formula of wave added resistance and CO2 emissions as functions of the environmental parameters (deadline: M09)
- V1 : use of simulator (subject to AF budget amendment)
- V2 : collection of raw data (either directly from company or through dedicated campaign)

EMSA

Miguel Madeira made clear that, in relation to MRV Regulation, “on a per-voyage basis” is mandatory at Monitoring while it is optional at Reporting in Thetis-MRV. However, if also reporting is done on a per-

voyage basis, then automatic data aggregation through the Thetis-MRV is possible². The rationale behind is that EMSA incentives collection of more granular data, to be analyzed for a more focused emission mitigation policy by the EU Commission.

Plenty of useful guidelines are already existing at DG Clima and are listed in slide #26 of Madeira presentation (see Sect.3.4 of this deliverable).

The Document of Compliance (DoC) is just a formal compliance statement with EU MRV Regulation, to be kept onboard. Miguel Madeira explained that some companies, in view of the forthcoming enforcement activities, are requesting their Verifiers for a DoC based on null emissions, in case emissions in previous calendar year are not within the scope of the Regulation.

There will be no amendment to MRV Regulation before the end of GUTTA project in 2021, but improvements on Thetis-MRV may be carried out, thus GUTTA might provide suggestions to further improvements of the system.

WP5

This is the verification and testing WP. The discussion focused on the new route and MRV deliverables.

As anticipated before the KO, it was made clear that MMPI cannot do the analysis of what new CB routes could be established on the basis of traffic data. This should be realized in cooperation with other partners. Josip Orović states that UniZd can help with storage and process of the traffic data, but all other PPs, especially CSA and AdSP should be involved in assessment of new routes.

Maračić suggests that also Port State Control has access to DoC, putting them at the same level of information of (Flag, Verifier).

It was suggested to collect end-user feedbacks on the eco-tool and MRV via online Monkey survey. Who will prepare them?

Resolutions:

The two deliverables on MRV guidelines could have the following contents:

² Company will always be liable even if automatic aggregation is used. This functionality is there to help but does not replace Company and Verifier responsibilities.

D.3.2.1. “Report on implementation challenges for MRV” could focus on MRV company’s barriers *before* using MRV. To bear in mind that the MRV company may not always be the Shipowner.

D.5.1.1. “Report on MRV life-cycle implementation potential and issues” could contain suggestions on how to improve user experience of Thetis-MRV. This could contribute to mitigate the burden arriving from Regulation itself, whose revision is an independent process. It is especially welcome by EMSA that such suggestions are done with reference to the voluntary module, as stated in the Executive Director’s letter for GUTTA (Feb.7, 2019)

Session D (March 8, 8:30-11:30)

This session comprised a part on WP1 and a hands-on demonstration of “slack” work environment.

WP1

As for the other WPs, activities and deliverables were first reviewed. Then, the main administrative rules from Programme Factsheet n.6 were presented.

The risk Register drafted in the AF was updated upon discussion with the PP representatives. Its current version is reported in Table 3. CMCC, as LP and out of its commitment for the Specific Objective on the eco-route tool, is exposed to all risks in the Register. It is in the interest of the GUTTA partnership to implement all risk mitigation actions for enhancing the chances of success of the project.

Table 3 Updated Risk Register after the ko meeting.

Risk-id	Risk description	Risk owners	Mitigation action
R0	Management-related risks: Impact of events like changes in timing of the activities, under- or overspending	CMCC, and all PP	-Full commitment of PP in the SC
R1	Lack or insufficient amount of passenger traffic data: Access to up-to-date CB passenger traffic data may result to be too limited for the aims of the project	CMCC, MMPI, AdSP	-Liaise with Agencija-zolpp located in Split - get access to historical RoPax data (e.g. years 2017-2018) - include data from High Speed Crafts and Cruise Ships

R2	Lack or insufficient amount or quality of vessel performance data: Vessel performance data might be obtained in insufficient quantity or in aggregated form only, making the assessment of their relationship to environmental conditions more uncertain	CMCC, UniZd, CSA	-use of ship simulator - dedicated on-board measurements
R3	Confidentiality and economic issues for MRV implementation: Legitimate economic interests by the shipowners may hamper their collaboration in defining guidelines for the MRV implementation	CMCC, CSA, MMPI	-interacting with EMSA in the early design stage of the GUTTA MRV guidance tool
R4	Delay in assessing the proper vessel response function	CMCC, UniZd	-Use of the layered approach described in WP3-4 resolutions

The key points of Factsheet n.6 were explained by Paola Agostini. They included:

- The principles for project management
- The project progress reporting
- The procedure for modifications and amendments
- The financial management
- The use of the SIU platform

These contents are presented in a structured way in the slides of Paola Agostini's presentation, which are shared along with the other KO material (cf. Sect. 3.4). PP administrative contact points have been advised to read and in-depth study Factsheet n.6.

A few administrative questions raised during this and previous sessions are answered in the following:

Q1: What is the total GUTTA budget for videos?

A1: In the AF, it is written about video or radio spots, we are not obliged to do both. In the budget breakdown, this cost item is often together with dissemination costs in general. A reasonable estimation is to have a total about 6,400 EUR for video/radio spots.

Q2: What does the 20%-flexibility rule exactly refer to?

A2: According to Factsheet n.6, “Increase of budget above 20% compared to the latest version of the approved AF in the following two cases:

- a. Increase of budget in any budget line
- b. Increase of budget in any work package“

Of course, the total ERDF contribution is not subject to the flexibility rule, which is just a budget re-allocation rule.

Q3: What are the conditions for applying for a major AF amendment?

A3: A major AF amendment can be applied for just once in the project lifetime and in following cases:

- budget reallocation among work packages and budget lines above the 20% flexibility limit
- prolongation of the project duration.

As any other major modification, it can be applied only after half of the project lifetime, in GUTTA case, after March 31, 2020.

Q4: Under which budget line should promotional USB sticks be reported?

A4: If they are meant as promotional materials, USB sticks should be reported as “External expertise & services” of WP2 (Communication). Please note that Promotional materials or gifts (small items related to promotion, communication, publicity or information) are eligible up to a maximum value of EUR 50 per item, they must be branded with the project logo (that includes the Programme logo) and they must be linked to promotion, communication, publicity or information activities.

Slack

Internal Communication is key to success of any project. Besides email and telephone, an instant messaging system is needed for informal and rapid information exchange among PPs.

To this end, Fabio Montagna made a practical introduction to slack (<https://slack.com/>) collaborative environment. It was first of all ensured that all present PPs made access to the “gutta-project” slack workspace. The main functionalities, including use of channels, citation, embedding of pictures, use of posts, use of “/” commands were reviewed by interactive use.

The exercise was really nice and satisfactory, cf. Figure 2. All PPs not yet on the slack account are encouraged to request access by email to gianandrea.mannarini@cmcc.it

Figure 2 Screenshot of the thread developed during the slack hands-on session

3.4 Online resources

The presentations of Sessions B-D were shared on google drive at the URL:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1xtX4kmqrUS5vtegfId7GSLYPP_53pGa

4. Conclusions

The GUTTA kick-off was a successful event with a significant participation from project partners and external stakeholders and citizens.

The opening conference, while highly contributing to the Communication strategy of the project, was also helpful for establishing links with other relevant European projects, in one case even within the Italy-Croatia Interreg Programme. Participation of 11 high-school students was a sign of an outreach including the under-40 EU population, which is an explicit target of the GUTTA project.

The internal meeting was a quite productive opportunity for deepening PP relationships and address implementation issues. Unfortunately, AdSP was not able to take part to it due to the subsidy contract not yet signed at the time of the KO. However, AdSP has been continuously informed on the progress of the project and will be integrated into the partnership through this report and dedicated meetings and webexes in the following months up to the next SC meeting.

The internal meeting also hosted participation of one EMSA representative, which accepted to be part of the GUTTA advisory board (cf. letter in Annex). In particular, EMSA provided advice on the specific objective of facilitation of MRV Regulation and offered support for related communication activities.

Annex

The Letter by EMSA is attached to this report.